

Comparative Studies On The Antibacterial Properties Of Diluted Crude Extract

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study is to observe whether the selected spices, turmeric, cumin, and cinnamon, could eradicate bacteria, serving as a substitute for chemical cleaning supplies. The methodology of this project begins with ethanol extraction of the spices, followed by the filtration to separate solids from the liquid. The liquid phase is then concentrated through hot evaporation. The next step is preparing the bacterial cultures in agar broth tubes. After allowing the bacteria to grow for two days, the concentrated spice extracts are added to three of the four tubes. The control tube is left without spice extract. Finally, the antibacterial efficacy of each extract will be measured by the turbidity of the tubes, indicating its bacterial growth, and determining the pH using pH strips. This data is compiled to analyze the impact of the spice extracts on bacterial growth. Due to the project not being completed in time, no data was found. Thus, implications can not be stated.

Keywords: Turmeric, Cumin, Cinnamon, Antibacterial Activity, Ethanol Extraction, Natural Cleaning Agents, Bacterial Growth Inhibition, Spice Extracts, Sustainable Cleaning Solutions, Alternative Disinfectants

CHAPTER I BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

1.1 Background of the Study:

Spices have been historically acknowledged for their strong antimicrobial properties and general safety when consumed, but their application as cleansers in contaminated areas has not been thoroughly investigated (De Vita & Lachowicz-Wisniewska, 2023). Previous studies have primarily focused on the antibacterial effects of isolated active ingredients or test spices against specific bacterial strains under ideal conditions rather than in the context of cleaning contaminated areas.

1.2. Statement of the Problem (SOP):

Can the following spices, when turned into diluted crude extracts, truly be used as an alternative to eliminate bacteria due to their antibacterial properties? If so, what spice is highly recommended for use in such a problem?

1. 3. Hypothesis:

We hypothesize that all spices can be used as an alternative to eliminate bacteria. Meanwhile, turmeric powder—when transformed into a diluted crude extract—is highly recommended as an alternative for cleaning contaminated areas due to its antibacterial properties compared to other spices.

1.4. Conceptual Framework:

CHAPTER II

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE AND STUDIES

2.1 Review of Related Literature:

This related literature is made up of statements and inspiration from this science journal, documented by Ram Kumar Pundir and Pranay Jain, who evaluated the antimicrobial activity of black pepper (*Piper nigrum*) and turmeric (*Curcuma longa*) extracts, focusing on their effectiveness against food-associated bacteria and fungi to explore these natural extracts as potential alternatives to chemical food preservatives. During the process, three solvents were used: water, 95% ethanol,

and 95% methanol, yielding six distinct extracts, which were then concentrated after filtration. The extracts' antimicrobial success was tested against food-borne bacteria: *Bacillus subtilis*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, and *Escherichia coli*, and fungal isolates from baked goods and pickles: *Aspergillus Luchuensis* and *Rhizopus stolonifer*. Antibacterial activity was determined by the zone of inhibition through agar well diffusion, and antifungal activity by percent mycelial growth inhibition using the poisoned food technique, with both being controlled. The duo found out that all six extracts have showcased antibacterial activity against all tested bacterial isolates, with the turmeric extract being strongly effective against *E. coli* isolates, while the black pepper being strongly effective against *Staphylococcus aureus* (Pundir & Jain, 2010). Other texts used are simply guides on how to create nutrient agar and are similar to a scientific journal by Ram Kumar Pundir and Pranay Jain, with an additional spice, garlic.

CHAPTER III METHODOLOGY

3.1. Methodology:

Materials used in this project:

- Gloves
- Cumin powder (250g)
- Cinnamon powder (250g)
- Turmeric powder (250g)
- Microscope (lab)
- Distilled water (200ml)
- 70% ethanol (2.2L)
- 1000ml Erlenmeyer flask (3)
- 250ml Erlenmeyer flask (3)
- 500ml beaker (3)
- Hot plate (3)
- Agar liquid broth
- PH strip
- Filter paper
- Metallic bowl (1)

Procedure:

- 1) Pour 250g of each spice powder into separate Erlenmeyer flasks.
- 2) After having 3 Erlenmeyer flasks (1000ml) filled with spices, pour 750ml of 70% ethanol into each flask.
- 3) Afterwards, cover the flasks with a clean wrap to prevent evaporation.
- 4) Wait 1 week before extracting.
- 5) After waiting, the spices would have settled, so use a stirring rod to prod at the spices and stir them so the spices would dilute in the liquid that settled on top.
- 6) Extract by pouring the mixture into the filter cloth while wearing gloves, letting the filter paper separate the solid spices from the extracted spice liquid.
- 7) Change the filter when the color of the paper turns into the saturated color of the mixture.
- 8) Perform this action until the liquid volume is 200 mL.

- 9) Do the same with the other extracts.
- 10) Collect the liquid and clear out the excess residue (such as spices).
- 11) Once liquid collection is complete, pour the liquid into a 500ml beaker for each liquid.
- 12) Fill a metal bowl halfway with water, then place the beakers inside so they are submerged.
- 13) Afterwards, use the hot plates and place the containers on top of them.
- 14) Slowly raise the temperature to 100 degrees Celsius.
- 15) At the fixed temperature, keep it on till there is nothing inside the char.
- 16) Do the same with the other liquids.
- 17) Note to stir well while it's heated.
- 18) Stir till the fumes no longer appear.
- 19) Moving on, prepare tubes of agar liquid broth to place bacteria inside them.
- 20) Drop 2 amount of bacteria inside the agar liquid broth.
- 21) Do the same with the other 3 tubes filled with agar liquid broth.
- 22) Wait 2 days for bacterial growth.
- 23) Afterwards, pour the diluted crude extract into the tubes.
- 24) Drop 2 amount of the extract, the same amount as the bacteria.
- 25) Again, do the same with the 3 tubes.
- 26) However, leave one without any spice inside the tube.
- 27) Afterwards, measure the data by how foggy the tubes get and their PH scale through a PH strip. 28) Then, compare the data available.

3.2 Research Design:

This research focuses on experimenting with different types of kitchen spices and turning them into diluted crude extract to investigate their effectiveness in eliminating bacteria. By observing and collecting data, we will assess the sterilization rate to determine if there are any changes in the bacteria collected, as indicated by their physical appearance and PH level, which will showcase the contribution to reducing bacterial growth. This experiment will be done by documenting the changes to achieve microbial depletion and the potential as an alternative to household cleaning supplies. Through the collection of unspecified and uncontrolled bacteria, this suggests that spices can eradicate bacteria in non-controlled circumstances.

3.3 Data Collection and Analysis:

The collected bacteria placed in the agar liquid broth tubes will be exposed to three different spices: cumin, turmeric, and cinnamon. The following tubes will be exposed to the same environment, presenting the fairness of the execution in this experiment. Furthermore, checking the PH level after the extracts come into contact with the bacteria will prove whether the bacteria die due to the acidity of the extract or not, providing fair data and results. Through observing, any changes will be recorded, such as the minor eradication of bacteria to a total

wipeout. From this, both qualitative and quantitative data collection will be used in this scientific investigation to take note of these observations.

**CHAPTER IV
PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION
OF DATA**

Tube	Data
1# – no spices	n/a PH Level: n/a
2# – turmeric spice	n/a PH Level: n/a
3# – cumin spice	n/a PH Level: n/a
4# – cinnamon spice	n/a PH Level: n/a

**CHAPTER V
SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION**

5.1. Summary:

Spices have always been considered to have elemental properties within different cultures, but science proves that some of these properties can actually be useful in society. Not only do they enrich the taste buds and give food some extra kick, but they can also assist in eliminating bacteria. The purpose of this experiment is to analyze the anti-bacterial properties of cinnamon, cumin, and turmeric to identify which would be the most effective in killing bacteria. After further consideration, the solid authentic spices were utilized and combined with ethanol in order to extract their spice properties into a liquid format, as using purchased spice extract could have other chemicals mixed in, which could affect the research. The makeshift spice extract was then tested in bacteria agar liquid broth and left for a couple of days to identify which spice has the most effective anti-bacterial properties based on the quantity of bacteria killed. According to this research, due to not being able to finish this science investigatory project on time, the most effective spice was not found.

5.2. Conclusion:

Due to no data given because of the lack of sufficient time, there is no clear answer to the hypothesis and research question.

5.3 Recommendation:

The limitations are definitely time, especially since the spices arrived later than usual, forcing a cramming and heavy change to this project. This may lead to a possible inaccuracy of results or to submitting the research later than the deadline. For this issue, ordering the spices as

early as you can would be recommended since time is limited, especially if the completion of the procedure is estimated to be done in a month or more.

Furthermore, something learned would include not stirring the mixture after it has settled (step 5), as it would have already been separated. Instead of mixing the entire liquid again before pouring it into the filter paper, only pour the settled liquid on top and try not to pour the solid parts settled at the bottom. This would lessen the amount of time it takes for the filter paper to filter out the re-stirred solid bits, and only have to filter out the current floating liquid to the new flask.

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